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School bikeability – what is it, and why is it important? An overview of key indicators and measurement

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ABSTRACT

Despite the theoretical recognition of children's specific needs regarding road safety, there remains a lack of literature focusing on children's bikeability or bikeability to school. This is rather concerning as many developed countries have witnessed a decline in active travel to school over the past few decades, despite the existence of well-recognized positive benefits of cycling for children. Recognising the significance of school travel, this study addresses this gap. Through an overview of existing literature, it discusses the importance of school bikeability and sheds light on its specific differences from general accessibility and bikeability, and identifies a set of indicators for measuring it. These indicators, categorised into four domains – Cycling Infrastructure, Connectivity and urbanisation, Safety, and Surrounding environment, can be further utilised to assess school bikeability in any given area. The results of such an assessment can be effectively used to guide investments and policies aimed at establishing safe and secure cycling routes to and from schools.

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Bikeability; school accessibility; urban cycling; built environment; children's accessibility

1. Introduction

In Europe, urban mobility accounts for 40% of all carbon dioxide emissions from road transport and up to 70% of other transport-related pollutants (Schipper et al., 2020). The transport sector thus lies at the heart of many sustainability and climate change strategies, including the European Green Deal (Fetting, 2020). A bicycle has been recognised as one of the most promising alternative means of transport for short and medium distances for several years already (Pucher & Buehler, 2008). Cycling has also been acknowledged as an important strategy to increase the insufficient level of physical activity and provide significant health benefits (OECD & World Health Organization, 2023). For children cycling to school, additional benefits such as heightened excitement and activation, improved well-being and life satisfaction have been observed (Friman et al., 2019; Westman, 2017). Despite this, in most developed countries, a decline rather than an

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increase in active travel to and from school has been observed over the past few decades (Ikeda et al., 2020; Westman et al., 2017). Since school travel, similar to commuting to work, constitutes regular and habitual journeys that account for a significant portion of travel, it is important to promote active mobility for these trips. Moreover, habits developed in the formative years are shown to have a lasting impact (Pucher & Buehler, 2012). In recognition, several cities, including Barcelona, London, Stockholm, and Bogotá, have focused on specific strategies and action plans to promote cycling to school (Ajuntament de Barcelona, n.d.; Stockholms Stad, n.d.; Thomas, 2022; Triana et al., 2019).

To devise a cycling strategy, various measures have been developed in recent years along with the concept of bikeability, building upon more developed research on walkability (Porter et al., 2020). Walking and cycling are often grouped together under the term non-motorised transport as they share some important determinants and benefits (Vale et al., 2016). However, they also present significant differences, such as required equipment, infrastructure, travel speed, distance coverage, safety threats and perceptions (Kellstedt et al., 2021). Bikeability indices, which enable the assessment of the bicycle friendliness of a location and consequently contribute to prioritising investments (Arellana et al., 2020; Munira et al., 2021), should therefore be examined separately from walkability indices. Although a modest number of various bikeability indices has been created (Castañón & Ribeiro, 2021; Vale et al., 2016; Valenzuela et al., 2022), existing indices rarely focus on specific groups of cyclists or use cases (such as children or inexperienced cyclists) but rather consider general bikeability and/or the general population. As emphasized by the United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF, 2022), children have different needs regarding road safety, which must be addressed distinctly in the cycling policy in order to reverse the decline in active travel to school. Given that the requirements for children's bikeability are often more stringent than those for other cyclists, enhancing conditions for school journeys can improve overall bikeability in the community (Watson & Dannenberg, 2008). Consequently, this can facilitate and encourage the uptake of cycling among the broader population not only among school children.

This paper discusses the current stage of knowledge on school bikeability, emphasizing the need to study school bikeability separately, and presents a list of indicators that should be helpful for practitioners and researchers studying school bikeability, and also children's bikeability in general. The paper does not aim to include every study published on children's cycling. However, it carefully emphasizes the needs of children and their caretakers in choosing cycling as the primary mode of transport to and from school, something that has been largely missing in current bikeability literature.

After defining what school bikeability is and noting how bikeability studies differ from general accessibility literature, the paper focuses on the following research questions: (1) What is bikeability and why is it important to consider bikeability for children, particularly concerning school travel? (2) What are the indicators to measure school bikeability and how do they differ from other existing bikeability indices? While the determinants of children cycling are complex, ranging from built environment attributes and their perception to social, economic, and cultural factors (Arellana et al., 2020), bikeability indices mostly focus on built environment factors, as does this study. Such indices enable measurement of school bikeability primarily through open-access data which increases their usability in practice.

The paper is structured as follows: In Section 2, the concept of (school) bikeability is explained. Section 3 discusses the importance of measuring bikeability and distinguishing between general bikeability and school bikeability for children. In Section 4, the paper suggests important indicators for constructing school bikeability indices and outlines possible ways to construct the index. Section 5 concludes with suggestions for future research.

2. What is it?

Bikeability has been defined by multiple authors across various fields, often also compared with bicycle accessibility (summarised in Table 1), making it challenging to discern a single consistent definition (Kellstedt et al., 2021; Schmid-Querg et al., 2021). In this section, we include a discussion of the definitions' distinctions and similarities to discern a definition of school bikeability for the purpose of this paper.

To begin with, the most common elements in the definitions of bikeability encompass aspects, such as conduciveness of the built environment, safety, and comfort or convenience for moving within an area or reaching desired destinations. However, significant differences exist. Castañon and Ribeiro (2021) differentiated bikeability definitions based on their functionality (focusing more on their use in assessment or characterisation) and spatial coverage (ranging from large to small zones, to networks to path segments). Besides the differences in spatial coverage evident in the definitions in Table 1, it is also apparent that the definitions vary in terms of the studied object. Bikeability has been considered both as a characteristic of an area and also of an individual (McNeil, 2011). Nielsen and Skov-Petersen (2018) note this by including both options in their bikeability definition. Another important difference lies in the consideration of the sole physical (built) environment (Grigore et al., 2019; Lowry et al., 2012) and other environments, such as social and cultural (Reggiani, 2022). Relatedly, definitions also differ in their consideration of objective (Krenn et al., 2015; Lowry et al., 2012) versus perceived aspects (Grigore et al., 2019; Reggiani, 2022).

Table 1. Definitions of bikeability used in recent studies.

Study	Definition of bikeability
Grigore et al. (2018, p. 3)	"The ability and convenience to reach important destinations by bike, based on perceived safety, comfort and attractiveness of the streets and intersections along the routes, as well as the travel distances".
Hamidi et al. (2019, p. 677)	"The ability to use a bicycle to access the main public transport station/stops".
Karolemeas et al. (2022)	The ability of the urban landscape to be biked.
Kellstedt et al. (2021, p. 212)	"The extent to which the actual and perceived environment is conducive and safe for bicycling".
Krenn et al. (2015)	Bicycle-friendliness of environments in terms of environmental characteristics.
Lowry et al. (2012, p. 41)	"An assessment of an entire bike network for perceived comfort and convenience and access to important destinations".
McNeil (2011)	The ability of an average person to meet his or her daily needs while getting around on a bicycle.
Nielsen and Skov-Petersen (2018, p. 36)	"The ability of a person to bike or the ability of the urban landscape to be biked".
Reggiani (2022)	The extent to which the actual and perceived, physical and cultural environment is adequate for the use of bicycles.
Winters et al. (2013)	Area's suitability for cycling.
Wysling and Purves (2022, p. 2)	"The potential of a region to encourage cycling based on the connectivity and accessibility to important destinations derived from bicycle suitability measures over a city".

Bikeability is closely related to other concepts, including bicycle suitability, bicycle friendliness, bicycle accessibility, bicycle comfort, and bicycle level of service (Castañón & Ribeiro, 2021; Lowry et al., 2012). While some authors consider bikeability as a superordinate concept, others use the terms bikeability, bicycle accessibility, and bicycle friendliness interchangeably (Hamidi et al., 2019). This study considers bikeability as a broader concept than accessibility, assessing more conditions. Bikeability is viewed here similarly to the definitions of Wysling and Purves (2022) and Karolemeas et al. (2022), as the ability of the urban landscape to accommodate cycling. However, adding the element of school means that the urban landscape needs to accommodate cycling of children. This, as discussed in the next chapter means that the environment should include the necessary preconditions that in the view of the caregiver are conducive to children's cycling, or at least enable it. This is being mindful of the fact that caregivers take a substantial role in the decision-making here (discussion further in section 3.2).

3. Why is it important?

Bikeability measures are elementary to assess the conditions for cycling, providing insights into why cycling levels may be low in certain areas and what improvements may be necessary to enhance bikeability. Such information is key for policy-makers and city planners, enabling them to prioritise efforts in the locations requiring the most significant improvements and in the forms deemed the most suitable (Arellana et al., 2020). The prioritisation of bicycle infrastructure investments is particularly crucial as municipalities (particularly small ones) often struggle with stringent budgets for cycling-related improvements. To provide actionable insights for planners and decision-makers, bikeability assessment tools need to be based on available data, require an adequate level of expertise for its use and interpretation, have low implementation costs, and be time-efficient (Kellstedt et al., 2021). In the subsections below we first discuss the added value of bikeability beyond traditional and generic accessibility measures and then specifically address school bikeability.

3.1. Bikeability beyond generic accessibility

While measuring general accessibility has been deemed important for decades (Geurs & Van Wee, 2004), such measures, focusing primarily on distance and travel time, have been criticised for being purposeful only for car-centric planning, and not capturing elements important for other modes, such as cycling (Handy, 2020; Lowry et al., 2012). Additionally to general infrastructure-based accessibility, measures aiming to account for comfort or convenience have been developed specifically for bicycling assessment. These include Bicycle Level of Service (BLOS) in the Highway Capacity Manual, 2010 and Bicycle Level of Traffic Stress (BLTS; Asadi-Shekari et al., 2013; Lowry et al., 2012). Even though more extensive, BLOS and BLTS still reflect primarily roadway characteristics, such as the number of lanes of traffic, the average volume of traffic, traffic speeds, characteristics related to parking, and the presence of a bike lane or a designated bicycle facility (Asadi-Shekari et al., 2013).

In addition to infrastructure-focused bicycle assessments, more recent bikeability measures pay particular attention to the human-centric elements of the physical

environment, such as safety and security, attractiveness, nature, and design. These bikeability assessment methods, including BikeScore®, Active Commuting Environment Scale, Mapping risk, The Bikeability and Walkability Evaluation table (see reviews by Castañon & Ribeiro, 2021; Kellstedt et al., 2021; Vale et al., 2016; and Valenzuela et al., 2022) combine various indicators into a designed algorithm to account for certain aspects relevant for cycling as a mode of transport, i.e. the attractiveness of the environment and safety (Kamel et al., 2020; Osama et al., 2020). Most studies categorise the indicators into similar domains, including (cycling) infrastructure; accessibility, land use and/or connectivity; safety; and topography or built environment (Castañon & Ribeiro, 2021; Vale et al., 2016; Valenzuela et al., 2022). The bikeability methodologies have thus moved away from the more traditionally used infrastructure-based cycling measurements that focus primarily on the travel impedance or discomfort caused by infrastructure and closely-related aspects (Vale et al., 2016), towards more complex measures focusing on the factors that can support or deter cycling in an area or context, and thus the area's bikeability. Such more complex, but still easily implementable measures are necessary to be developed in order to move away from car-centric planning towards planning for sustainable travel modes (Handy, 2020).

From the context perspective, we observe that the bikeability studies originate from diverse urban environments, and the authors explicitly select indicators applicable to the local contexts, such as Arellana et al. (2020) for cities in the Global South, Wout (2022) and Hartanto (2017) for Dutch cities and Munira et al. (2021) and Porter et al., 2020 for car-dependent Austin, Texas. However, as discussed in the next chapter, focusing on heterogeneity occurring due to personal factors has been rather rare.

3.2. Children's bikeability to school

Children's abilities to interpret complex traffic situations may be limited due to their still-developing visual, motor, and cognitive skills. This may lead to challenges in focusing attention, understanding others' intentions, and accurately assessing risk (Evans & Norman, 2003; Gorrini et al., 2023; Rosenbloom et al., 2008). Children therefore have unique mobility needs that must be acknowledged when planning for cycling (McMillan, 2007; Mitra, 2013; UNICEF, 2022).

School journeys represent a significant portion of children's travel (Pooley et al., 2010). As such, they can have considerable impacts both on children's health and on the environment. Addressing these areas is especially important for meeting the Green Deal goal and reaching the recommended levels of physical activity. According to the European Declaration on Cycling, cycling holds considerable potential to support decarbonisation of urban transport and thus help achieve carbon neutrality by 2050, as noted in the Green Deal (Fetting, 2020). The level of physical activity among children is currently often insufficient, as it does not reach the recommended 60 min a day (WHO, 2020). For instance, in the UK during the 2020/2021 school year, similarly to the previous years, only about 45% of children and adolescents aged 5–16 met the recommended levels of physical activity (GOV-UK, 2022).

School journeys thus present a prime opportunity for improvements in cycling infrastructure, which could yield substantial benefits. Furthermore, schools are recognised as important places for habit formation. Encouraging walking and cycling to school can

therefore help children become familiar with these travel modes at an early age (Alm & Koglin, 2022; Biondi et al., 2022). The importance of promoting cycling among children is further emphasized as habits formed during childhood are likely to persist into and throughout adulthood (Johansson, 2005; Pucher & Buehler, 2012). Addressing children's travel habits may thus contribute to more sustainable mobility across generations. Additionally, improvements to school routes will not only improve bikeability for children travelling to school but also benefit other cyclists in the area (Watson & Dannenberg, 2008). Because school travel often coincides with peak commuting times, it significantly contributes to morning congestion (Carver et al., 2013). In the United States, it was found that school-related travel accounts for 10–16% of all private vehicles on the roads within the country (McDonald et al., 2011), thus highlighting another reason why enhancing school bikeability can be beneficial.

Unlike adults, who typically make their own travel decisions, the mode choice for children travelling to school and their independence when travelling is rarely solely the children's choice (Gong et al., 2024; McMillan, 2005; Mitra, 2013). According to McMillan's framework (2005), mediating factors such as neighbourhood safety, traffic safety, and household transportation options are moderated by parental perceptions, social and cultural norms, attitudes, and sociodemographic factors, and this interaction influences the decision regarding the children's travel mode. The significant effect of parental attitudes has been evidenced empirically; specifically, in Davis, California, the caregivers' constraints to participate in different activities (i.e. work), their willingness to drive or escort their children, and their encouragement to cycle significantly impacted the choice of their children's travel mode (Emond & Handy, 2012). Data from a school travel survey in Oregon showed that parental attitudes towards walking and cycling, as well as car use, significantly impact children's probability of walking or cycling to school, when important environmental variables are controlled for (Yang & Markowitz, 2012). Swiss data revealed that a young person is much more likely to cycle if their parents also cycle (Schmassmann et al., 2024).

Depending on the child's age, the caregiver may play a smaller or greater role in the decision-making, and in some cases, the decision may entirely be made by the caregiver (Mitra, 2013). Caretakers' decisions and preferences not only affect current travel modes but can also impact the future ones, as children often adopt their parents' preferences and attitudes (Fitch et al., 2019; Mitra, 2013).

Some parents who prefer to escort their children to school, often by car, do so due to safety concerns (Trapp et al., 2011). However, in doing so they inadvertently contribute to higher traffic congestion, and to creating an environment around the school they perceive as unsafe (Carver et al., 2013; Gössling et al., 2024; Lang et al., 2011). Thus, the trend of increased parental escort to school fosters a vicious circle that impacts the perception and practice of bikeability to school, further discouraging children (Rothman et al., 2021).

Although the importance of planning for children's cycling, with their caregivers in mind, has been established, to the best of our knowledge, a specific bikeability index focusing on younger children is lacking. While most current methods for assessing cycling environments incorporate a variety of indicators and differ in their methodology and focus area (see Table 2 below for a summary of the reviewed bikeability index measures), the differences seem to be less pronounced in terms of heterogeneity of focus groups. Few researchers distinguish between commuters and recreational cyclists, low- and high-

Table 2. Summary of reviewed studies focusing on bikeability indices.

Author (year)	Location	Tool	Unit of analysis	Aim	Domains	Weighting method
Arellana et al. (2020)	Barranquilla, Colombia	Bikeability index	Road network	To assess and prioritise bicycle infrastructure investments in cities of Global South, based on different types of cyclists.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Directness and coherence • Comfort and attractiveness • Traffic safety • Climate • Presence of bike infrastructure • Security • Cost of trip 	Results from ranking surveys
Asadi-Shekari et al. (2015)	Singapore, Malaysia	Bicycle Safety Index	Street segments and intersections	To evaluate bicycle safety of street segments and intersections.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bicycle safety 	Depth of evaluation and number of guidelines considering each indicator
Hardinghaus et al. (2021)	Berlin	Spatial bikeability Index	Statistical units	To develop a spatial bikeability index based on open data.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Road types • Street connectivity • Biking facilities • Green pathways • Other cycle facilities 	Expert survey ranking
Codina et al. (2022)	Barcelona	Built environment bikeability Index	100 × 100 m grid	To map bikeability potential of Barcelona as a high-dense, compact, Mediterranean style city.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traffic • Infrastructure • Connectivity • Parking spaces • Topography 	Findings from literature, survey answers
Bijl (2022)	Nijmegen, Netherlands	Bikeability geospatial index	Raster layer, and neighbourhoods	To assess bikeability of Nijmegen, reviewing index from Winters et al. (2013).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quality of cycling infrastructure • Connectivity • Destination accessibility • Elevation difference • Junctions 	Interviews

(Continued)

Table 2. Continued.

Author (year)	Location	Tool	Unit of analysis	Aim	Domains	Weighting method
Karolemeas et al. (2022)	Athens, Greece	Bikeability Index	Road sections	To evaluate the ability to cycle in the urban environment of Greek cities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Road network • Urban environment • Level of Service 	Using analytical hierarchy process presented to cyclists
Tijana et al. (2023)	Novi Sad, Serbia	Bikeability Index	200 × 200 m grid	To assess the favourability of Novi Sad for the development of sustainable types of traffic.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cycling infrastructure • Land use and accessibility • Security • Environment 	Survey
Munira et al. (2021)	Austin, Texas	Bikeability Index	Buffer zones of 161, 804 m, and 1 609 m circular radius around intersections	To assess bike-friendliness of the bike network to improve performance of demand models for bicycle traffic.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cycling infrastructure • Comfort • Destination density • Transit coverage 	Equal weights
Ros-McDonnell et al. (2020)	La Manga del Mar Menor and Cartagena, Spain	Biking Index	Bike lane segments	To develop a mobility index oriented to the use of bicycles in Mediterranean coastal tourist cities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Characteristics of the segment • Road crossings • Obstructions • Safety • Signalling and lightning • Connection and distribution 	Equal weights
Winters et al. (2013)	Metro Vancouver Region	Bikeability Index	10 × 10 m raster layers combined into neighbourhood index	To identify areas more or less conducive to cycling.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bicycle facility availability • Bicycle facility quality • Street connectivity • Topography • Land use 	Focus groups, but in the end given equal weights

Motta (2017)	Curitiba	Bikeability Index	Raster map with 10 × 10 m grid, and average index per neighbourhood	To highlight areas more or less conducive to cycling.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Residential density • Land-use • Topography • Safety • Type of infrastructure 	Questionnaire, principal component analysis
Ito and Biljecki (2021)	Singapore, Tokyo	Bikeability Index	Buffer zones of various radius around sample points	To assess bikeability using street view imagery and computer vision.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Connectivity • Environment • Infrastructure • Perception • Vehicle-cyclist interaction 	Equal weights
Kamel et al. (2020)	Vancouver	Bike Composite Index	Traffic Analysis Zones	To develop an index that would account for cyclist-vehicle crash risk.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Attractiveness • Safety 	Multiple regression
Porter et al. (2020)	Austin, Texas and Birmingham, Alabama	Bikeability Index	1,5 and 3 km street network buffer around residential addresses	To develop transportation and recreation bikeability indices.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bicycle infrastructure • Population and residential densities • Distance to amenities • Cycling mode share 	Survey data
Krenn et al. (2015)	Graz, Austria	Bikeability Index	100 × 100 m grid, also considering surrounding cells	To develop a bikeability index for mid-size European city.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cycling infrastructure • Topography • Land-use mix 	Equal
Langerød Rugtvedt (2019)	Grenland region, Norway	Bikeability Index	Road segments	To create a bikeability index, with sensitivity towards different user groups.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bicycle infrastructure • Road characteristics • Topography • Connectivity • Street amenities 	Survey, weight assigned according to different user groups

(Continued)

Table 2. Continued.

Author (year)	Location	Tool	Unit of analysis	Aim	Domains	Weighting method
Hartanto (2017)	Arnhem/ Nijmegen region	Bikeability index to assess TOD nodes	Buffer zones of 800, 1600, and 2400 m radius from transit stops	To develop a bikeability index that enables assessment of transit-orientedness around transit nodes.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traffic condition • Connectivity • Infrastructure • Environment • Topography • Bicycle parking 	Equal weights
Lin and Wei (2018)	Taipei City	Bikeability assesment	City administrative unit	To evaluate bike friendliness within an area, avoiding interdepen-dency issues.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facility suitability • Environmental amenity • Destination accessibility 	Analytical hierarchical process
Schmid-Querg et al. (2021)	Munich	Bikeability Index	Raster cells with resolution of 1 × 1 m	To develop a model to measure bikeability in urban areas.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bicycle infrastructure • Speed limits • Parking facilities • Intersection infrastructure 	Interviews
Winters et al. (2016)	US and Canadian cities	Bike Score	City	To assess association between urban bikeability and cycling behaviour.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cycling infrastructure • Topography • Amenities • Road connectivity • Bicycle mode share 	Random
Wout (2022)	Eindhoven, Netherlands	Bikeability assessment tool	Neighbourhoods	To develop a bikeability index to assess bikeability of a Dutch neighbourhood.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bicycle infrastructure • Junction infrastructure • Bicycle parking • Environment • Accessibility 	Random

More detailed summarisation of the respective domains and indicators used in the studies can be found in Appendix 1.

income citizens, or cyclists and non-cyclists (Arellana et al., 2020; Motta, 2017; Porter et al., 2020), but there is a noticeable lack of specific metrics focusing on children or cycling to primary or middle schools. An exception is a study by Langerød Rugtvedt (2019) which differentiates between experienced cyclists, school children, people with reduced mobility, and e-bikers. The authors found no profound variability in the preferences among the groups, which, however, could have been due to poor data availability, as some indicators had to be proxied by available but less fitting data. Few other studies relevant to assessing school bike accessibility exist. Hull (2020) only examines travel time differences between school accessibility in winter versus in summer; Goodman et al. (2019) consider the propensity of cycling to school in England based on route distance and hilliness, but do not consider the current state of the road network; Shaaban and Abdur-Rouf (2020) use a qualitative audit tool, not quantitative spatial data to assess the propensity of cycling around schools in Doha, Qatar; Sisson et al. (2006) do not focus on an index creation; and Rahman et al. (2020) focus on a conceptual framework for modelling safe cycling routes to high schools only. A comprehensive objective school bikeability assessment applicable to younger children remains to be developed.

Since schools are significant daily destinations for children and they have the capacity to influence both children's and parents' behaviour, this work focuses on providing a background for creating a bikeability index centred around schools. Given that the requirements for children's bikeability are often more stringent than those for other cyclists, enhancing conditions for school journeys can improve overall bikeability in the community. The following section proposes a set of indicators that could, in a further study, be used to create a school bikeability index. Such an index could be used for assessing the bikeability of the environment between home and school destinations.

4. Measuring school bikeability – important indicators and potential index suggestions

The key indicators used in this study are based on existing bikeability literature that documents the importance of certain bikeability indicators, and further evidence was searched for to find indicators catering to the needs of children. Building upon existing literature on children's cycling to school and bikeability studies seems relevant, even though some authors have also derived their indicators from primary data such as street guidelines (Asadi-Shekari et al., 2015), experts' opinions and focus groups (Arellana et al., 2020; Hardinghaus et al., 2021), general bike-user survey (Codina et al., 2022), or field observations and interviews with commuters (Schmid-Querg et al., 2021). Additionally, insights from School Walkability Indices developed by Lee et al. (2020) and Giles-Corti et al. (2011) were included in this study when deemed relevant.

Similar to most current studies, this research focuses primarily on objective indicators that can be measured through observation or spatial data, enabling replicability and generalizability since open-source data are in most cases available for these indicators. It is also a relatively straightforward, fast, and cost-effective way of measurement. This approach bypasses the drawbacks of indices with data derived from surveys, interviews, or audits, which require significant time for data collection and are often subject to sampling and response biases (Krenn et al., 2015), even though suggestions for more subjective data types are also suggested in some instances. The indicators here are divided

into four domains – Cycling infrastructure, Connectivity and urbanisation, Safety, and Surrounding environment – consistent with previous studies (Castañon & Ribeiro, 2021; Valenzuela et al., 2022).

4.1. Cycling infrastructure

One of the most frequently referenced indicators in bikeability indices, and particularly related to children cycling, is the presence of cycling infrastructure. Table 3 below summarises the indicators related to cycling infrastructure. The presence of such infrastructure is usually measured either by considering the total length of cycleways in a given area, or by assessing the percentage of roadways in the area that are suitable for cycling (Castañon & Ribeiro, 2021). Although any type of cycling infrastructure is beneficial, the type of infrastructure has been found to play a role in shaping the cyclists' behaviour. Aldred (2015), by using an online questionnaire to study the urban context in the UK, explored how different types of cycling infrastructures influence parents' decisions to allow their children to cycle. The study revealed that parents are significantly more likely to allow their 12-year-old children to cycle when the cycling infrastructure is physically separated from motorised traffic. Interestingly, while adults have a 76% preference to cycle on residential streets without dedicated cycling infrastructure when cycling themselves, only 25% of them would allow their children to cycle on these streets.

The width of cycle paths is crucial for both comfort and safety. Wider paths allow parents and/or children to cycle alongside each other, an option many parents may prefer (Ghekiere et al., 2014). Additionally, paths that are wider – ideally at least 2.5 m – are easier to maintain and clear of snow. This aspect is particularly relevant in regions experiencing significant snowfall, where proper snow removal can significantly influence the mode share of cycling (Hull, 2020). The pavement type and quality are important due to the physical effort that needs to be exerted and the risk of slipping on open surfaces. A high-quality surface is a closed pavement (asphalt and concrete) without larger potholes or cracks. A low-quality surface includes pavement stones, gravel roads, or any other non-smooth pavement, or a closed pavement with a significant number of holes and cracks (Rahman et al., 2020). Such low-quality surfaces require both higher effort and thus reduce comfort, but also pose higher risks of slipping and accidents, especially for children and in bad weather conditions (Ghekiere et al., 2014).

Bicycle infrastructure at intersections is cited as frequently as the general presence of bicycle paths as a factor influencing bikeability. This is unsurprising, given that 60% of bicyclist fatalities involve car, with most fatalities occurring at intersections (Reurings et al., 2012).

However, the quality and thus safety of the cycling infrastructure at intersections are seldom discussed in bikeability indices (Schmid-Querg et al., 2021). Bicycle infrastructure at intersections exists in many different forms, varying in terms of traffic volumes, traffic designs, and available space, making it challenging to categorise according to preference (Castañon & Ribeiro, 2021). One simple approach to assessing intersections is to count how many bicycle-friendly connections exist at intersections. For example, Munira et al. (2021) and Winters et al. (2013) considered important the number of intersections with at least three legs where one or more roads are suitable for cycling. A more thorough assessment of intersections might consider safety features such as roundabouts, priority

Table 3. School bikeability index, indicators related to cycling infrastructure.

Indicator	Necessary data	Impact	Reference ^a
Presence of bicycle infrastructure	A dataset detailing the location of cycling infrastructure, not necessarily distinguished by type, and a road network dataset.	Positive.	(1) (Arellana et al., 2020; Asadi-Shekari et al., 2015; Castañon & Ribeiro, 2021; Codina et al., 2022; Hardinghaus et al., 2021; Hartanto, 2017; Ito & Biljecki, 2021; Kamel et al., 2020; Krenn et al., 2015; Lin & Wei, 2018; Munira et al., 2021; Porter et al., 2020; Schmid-Querg et al., 2021; Tijana et al., 2023; Winters et al., 2013, 2016; Wout, 2022) (2) (De Meester et al., 2014; Ji et al., 2022; Rahman et al., 2020; Shaaban & Abdur-Rouf, 2020; Wangzom et al., 2023) (3) (Giles-Corti et al., 2011)
Type of bicycle infrastructure	A dataset detailing the type of all segments of available bicycle infrastructure. The typology should be based on the built characteristics (shared street, bicycle lane, shared or exclusive bicycle path), rather than on the use type (main vs local network).	Certain types of infrastructure are preferable.	(1) (Arellana et al., 2020; Bijl, 2022; Hartanto, 2017; Krenn et al., 2015; Langerød Rugtvedt, 2019; Lin & Wei, 2018; Motta, 2017; Munira et al., 2021; Ros-McDonnell et al., 2020; Schmid-Querg et al., 2021; Tijana et al., 2023; Winters et al., 2013, 2016; Wout, 2022) (2) (Aldred, 2015; Shaaban & Abdur-Rouf, 2020; Sisson et al., 2006)
Width of bicycle paths	A dataset specifying the width of available bicycle paths.	Wider cycle paths are preferable.	(1) (Arellana et al., 2020; Ito & Biljecki, 2021; Langerød Rugtvedt, 2019; Lin & Wei, 2018; Wout, 2022) (2) (Ghekiere et al., 2014; Rahman et al., 2020; Sisson et al., 2006)
Pavement type and quality	A dataset describing the type of pavement of existing bicycle infrastructure. Additionally, a subjective quality assessment of the pavement might be used.	Smooth, closed surface pavements are preferable.	(1) (Asadi-Shekari et al., 2015; Hartanto, 2017; Ito & Biljecki, 2021; Langerød Rugtvedt, 2019; Ros-McDonnell et al., 2020; Wout, 2022) (2) (Ghekiere et al., 2014; Hull, 2020; Rahman et al., 2020; Sisson et al., 2006)
Quality of bicycle infrastructure at intersections	A dataset describing the presence and type of bicycle infrastructure at intersections (e.g. bicycle passages and crossings, and traffic lights for cyclists).	Positive.	(1) (Asadi-Shekari et al., 2015; Hartanto, 2017; Ito & Biljecki, 2021; Munira et al., 2021; Ros-McDonnell et al., 2020; Schmid-Querg et al., 2021; Winters et al., 2013; Wout, 2022) (2) (Aranda-Balboa et al., 2020; De Meester et al., 2014; De Vries et al., 2010; Dessing et al., 2016; Huertas-Delgado et al., 2017; Rahman et al., 2020; Wangzom et al., 2023) (3) (Lee et al., 2020)
Signage/ signalling	A dataset of signage presence, plus a potential readability and usefulness assessment.	Positive.	(1) (Asadi-Shekari et al., 2015; Ros-McDonnell et al., 2020)
Bicycle parking		Positive.	

(Continued)

Table 3. Continued.

Indicator	Necessary data	Impact	Reference ^a
	A dataset on the presence of bicycle parking. Ideally specifying its size and type.		(1) (Castañon & Ribeiro, 2021; Hartanto, 2017; Ito & Biljecki, 2021; Lin & Wei, 2018; Ros-McDonnell et al., 2020; Schmid-Querg et al., 2021; Wout, 2022) (2) (Shaaban & Abdur-Rouf, 2020)
Obstacles on bicycle paths	An objective dataset on the presence of obstacles such as bollards and gates, and construction work. Plus a subjective assessment on obstructions, such as illegally parked cars.	Negative.	(1) (Arellana et al., 2020; Asadi-Shekari et al., 2015; Ito & Biljecki, 2021; Wout, 2022)

^aIn reference column, (1) refers to references from studies focusing on bikeability indices, (2) refers to studies focusing on determinants of cycling of children and cycling to school, (3) refers to studies on school walkability indices.

squares, the type of regulation (e.g. markings, signs, traffic lights, or priority rules), and the type of cycling infrastructure (e.g. separated bicycle paths, bicycle boxes, bicycle lanes, bicycle dedicated traffic lights, and median islands), as illustrated by Wout (2022). This detailed categorisation seems especially important for children and their parents and would be recommended if data availability allows.

Bicycle parking, though less frequently considered in bikeability indices (Castañon & Ribeiro, 2021), can be crucial for commuting journeys, like school trips (Veilette et al., 2018). Studies from the Netherlands even categorise different types of parking facilities and examine their characteristics, such as design, cost, occupancy, or security (Hartanto, 2017; Wout, 2022).

Obstacles on bicycle paths both obstruct the ease of cycling and present safety hazards (Arellana et al., 2020). However, the impact of such obstacles may differ depending on the user. For instance, a bollard on a separate cycle path may present a different type of danger compared to a car parked in a cycle lane alongside a busy road. Such analysis seems to be missing. While some types of obstacles could be identified objectively from a dataset of such obstacles, the aspect may also require more complex, subjective, assessment along the network.

Moreover, several studies (Codina et al., 2022; Hardinghaus et al., 2021; Karolemeas et al., 2022; Wout, 2022) have included bike-sharing facilities as an aspect of bikeability, focusing on factors such as the density of stations or the shortest distance to a certain destination. However, public bike-sharing schemes appear irrelevant when considering children travelling to school as shared bicycles are generally not designed for children's use.

4.2. Connectivity and urbanisation

A well-connected network of bicycle-friendly streets increases cycling comfort, enhances safety, and reduces the time required to reach certain destinations (Yang et al., 2019). Parents have also indicated a preference for having multiple route options for their children to cycle (Ghekiere et al., 2014). The higher connectivity then enables them to choose a route that is perceived as more suitable. Analyses of

the route connectivity, the availability of multiple cycle-friendly paths, or the comparison of used paths to the shortest paths can be easily conducted if data on trip origins and destinations are available. However, as this may often not be the case, connectivity is then related to the density of intersections with cycling infrastructure, as mentioned in the previous section. Furthermore, trip origin-destination data can be highly useful when assessing bikeability to school, as perceived safety depends on the number of intersections along a school route. Therefore, while higher street connectivity is beneficial as it offers more possibilities, it also means higher intersection density, which may be perceived negatively (Ghekiere et al., 2014). It is therefore necessary to account for both these effects.

Level of urbanisation is important as it has been positively related to active travel due to its association with increased social interaction, more commercial activity, and improved access to transport systems (Forsyth et al., 2007). The social interaction resulting from higher population density seems especially important in the context of children cycling to school, as two important determinants mentioned are social safety and opportunities for social interactions with friends on the way to school (Aranda-Balboa et al., 2020; Wangzom et al., 2023). At the same time, high population density may also affect bikeability to school negatively due to higher potential for collisions. It may therefore be important to define a range in which population density appears to increase bikeability.

Additionally, higher population density is also linked to certain land uses that might negatively affect active travel to school for children, such as commercial, institutional, or industrial land use (Broberg & Sarjala, 2015; Scheiner et al., 2019; Wangzom et al., 2023). Yet, the effects of land use seem to be mixed (De Meester et al., 2014), and there is an evidence suggesting that land-use variables impact adults' daily activities more than children's daily commute to school (Schlossberg et al., 2006).

Another often-cited factor contributing to bikeability is destination accessibility or destination density. When assessing areas around schools, the primary focus is the destination itself (the school). Accessibility to other mentioned destinations is thus generally not considered.

Indicators related to connectivity and urbanisation are summarised in [Table 4](#).

Table 4. School bikeability index, indicators related to connectivity and urbanisation.

Indicator	Necessary data	Impact	Reference ¹
Street connectivity/ Intersection density	A road network dataset.	Positive.	(1) (Bijl, 2022; Hardinghaus et al., 2021; Kamel et al., 2020; Langerød Rugtvedt, 2019; Lin & Wei, 2018; Winters et al., 2016; Wout, 2022) (2) (Buttazzoni et al., 2019; Ghekiere et al., 2014; Mitra, 2013; Scheiner et al., 2019) (3) (Lee et al., 2020)
Degree of urbanisation	Population density data at a spatial grid.	Positive.	(1) (Motta, 2017; Porter et al., 2020; Tijana et al., 2023; Wout, 2022) (2) (Aranda-Balboa et al., 2020; De Meester et al., 2014; Schlossberg et al., 2006; Wangzom et al., 2023) (3) (Lee et al., 2020)

4.3. Safety

As noted earlier, safety – both traffic safety and social safety – plays a crucial role in children’s bikeability to school. While traffic safety can be more easily indicated by various objective indicators, social safety indicators require more subjective judgements and are less often accounted for.

The most commonly cited aspect of traffic safety seems to be the maximum traffic speed, which is measured on the roads that run alongside or cross bicycle paths. Higher speed limits are associated with a lower probability of a child cycling to school and a higher probability of an adult escort (McMillan, 2007; Scheiner et al., 2019). Traffic speed is also related to road type and traffic volume. While measuring traffic volumes may provide a better indication of road congestion and thus people’s perception of safety, such data may not be readily available for most roads across a city at various times during the day. Thus, road type is often used to assess potential safety threats. Although preferences for road type vary, there is generally a tendency to prioritise quieter residential streets over main roads, due to the lower traffic of large vehicles such as busses and trucks (Ghekiere et al., 2014). Previous studies have used different indicators (or a combination thereof) to account for this association, such as a main road without any parallel bicycle infrastructure (Krenn et al., 2015), a density of roads with favourable versus unfavourable speed limits and road categories (Langerød Rugtvedt, 2019), or the percentage of quieter road types compared to more major roads (Hardinghaus et al., 2021). These specific measurements often have to be chosen as proxies due to the unavailability of more suitable data. The maximum speed limits may not fully reflect real speeds in some places, so in addition to low maximum speed limits or the presence of quieter roads, some studies also mention the availability of speed-measuring devices or speed-limiting measures to help further maintain low speeds (Ito & Biljecki, 2021; Shaaban & Abdur-Rouf, 2020).

Bicycle traffic flow is important due to the “safety-in-numbers effect” which suggests that a higher volume of cyclists on the streets increases the overall visibility of cyclists and helps other road users to be better prepared to safely interact with cyclists (Codina et al., 2022). If data on bicycle traffic flow are unavailable, this aspect can be operationalised by measuring the mode share in an area (Winters et al., 2016). A greater presence of pedestrians can also contribute to increased social safety, as there are more “eyes on the street”, creating a sense of community and safety when others are also using active mobility (Aranda-Balboa et al., 2020). At the same time, high bicycle traffic flow may create potential threats in the form of collisions between bicyclists.

Fewer collisions lead to better bikeability (Codina et al., 2022). Various methods have been adopted to measure this, such as the ratio of bike collisions per bicycle trips in a grid cell (Codina et al., 2022) or the density of streets where crashes have occurred (Lee et al., 2020). In contrast, Scheiner et al. (2019) found that accident hot spots might be a better indicator of children’s independent mobility compared to a mere number of injuries along a route.

The location of the school entrance, together with school zone marking, are crucial for promoting cycling to school (Shaaban & Abdur-Rouf, 2020). The school entrance should be located in a way that the number of safety conflict points is minimised. Studies have also shown that additional interventions alongside on-the-ground painted signs or static

road signs announcing school zones are needed to impact travelling speeds and, consequently, safety. These interventions may include law enforcement, crossing guards, automatic speed enforcement, or physical interventions for traffic calming (Rothman et al., 2022; Strawderman et al., 2015).

Table 5 below summarises the indicators related to safety.

4.4. Surrounding environment

The most common indicator of the surrounding environment included in the bikeability indices is slope or hilliness, as steeper slopes require more physical effort to ride a bicycle, thus reducing comfort (Arellana et al., 2020). Surprisingly, the indicator seems to be less frequently mentioned when considering children's cycling. In addition to comfort, hilliness or steepness have also been highlighted by parents due to the increased risk of accidents when gaining speed while cycling downhill (Ghekiere et al., 2014). The variable can be measured in various ways, including assigning specific scores to different slope percentages (Arellana et al., 2020; Krenn et al., 2015), calculating the ratio of bicycle lanes with low slope percentages to all lanes (Hartanto, 2017), recording the minimum and maximum slope values (Ito & Biljecki, 2021), or using the average slope (Lin & Wei, 2018).

The presence of natural elements has been more often reflected in studies focusing on children. Natural elements can take many forms such as trees, parks (or green spaces in general), and bodies of water. While most studies consider these elements for their visual appeal, some also examine their functional aspects, like providing shade (Lin & Wei, 2018). In order for green spaces and other natural elements to positively influence active mobility, they need to be well maintained (Krenn et al., 2015). Otherwise, they might have a counterproductive effect on bikeability. Parents again seem more concerned about the safety risks associated with these elements, such as causing distractions, rather than focusing on their aesthetic qualities or capacities to provide enjoyment (Ghekiere et al., 2014). However, the maintenance of green spaces, similar to perceived aesthetics and safety of the environment, is subject to a highly subjective judgement requiring subjective data for evaluation.

Air quality can also influence people's decision whether to cycle or not (Zhao et al., 2018), and it has been included as an indicator in bikeability studies, for example, through the Air Quality Index (Ito & Biljecki, 2021; Wout, 2022). However, Tainio et al. (2016) noted that only a small number of cities worldwide suffer from air pollution levels that pose health threats that would outweigh the health benefits of cycling. Air quality can be highly associated with the levels of traffic congestion, making traffic congestion a potential proxy for air quality (Lin & Wei, 2018).

Table 6 summarises indicators related to the surrounding environment.

4.5. Measurement possibilities

The indicators proposed in the previous sections aim to serve as a basis for creating a school bikeability index based primarily on geospatial data. This index can be either applied to specific school routes identified from an origin-destination trip matrix (Ros-McDonnell et al., 2020), administrative spatial units, such as neighbourhoods, (Hardinghaus et al., 2021), or other, self-defined, areas around schools (Ito & Biljecki, 2021).

Table 5. School bikeability index, indicators related to safety.

Indicator	Necessary data	Impact	Reference ¹
Traffic control devices and speed limiting measures	A dataset on locations of such devices and measures.	Positive.	(1) (Arellana et al., 2020; Ito & Biljecki, 2021; Kamel et al., 2020; Wout, 2022) (2) (Rothman et al., 2022; Shaaban & Abdur-Rouf, 2020)
Bicycle traffic volume	A data on bicycle traffic volumes measures at various places across the city.	Positive.	(1) (Arellana et al., 2020; Codina et al., 2022; Kamel et al., 2020; Porter et al., 2020; Winters et al., 2016)
Traffic volume	A data on traffic volumes with high-enough density of measuring points.	Negative.	(1) (Arellana et al., 2020; Ito & Biljecki, 2021; Kamel et al., 2020; Karolemeas et al., 2022; Langerød Rugtvedt, 2019; Lin & Wei, 2018; Munira et al., 2021) (2) (Bao et al., 2023; Rahman et al., 2020; Sisson et al., 2006) (3) (Giles-Corti et al., 2011; Lee et al., 2020)
Lightning	A dataset on the availability of public street lightning.	Positive.	(1) (Arellana et al., 2020; Asadi-Shekari et al., 2015; Hartanto, 2017; Ito & Biljecki, 2021; Langerød Rugtvedt, 2019; Lin & Wei, 2018; Wout, 2022) (2) (Timperio et al., 2006) (3) (Lee et al., 2020)
Traffic speed	A dataset on the maximum allowed traffic speed for each road segment.	Negative.	(1) (Asadi-Shekari et al., 2015; Karolemeas et al., 2022; Langerød Rugtvedt, 2019; Munira et al., 2021; Schmid-Querg et al., 2021; Wout, 2022) (2) (Bao et al., 2023; De Meester et al., 2014; Ghekieri et al., 2014; McMillan, 2007; Rahman et al., 2020; Scheiner et al., 2019; Shaaban & Abdur-Rouf, 2020; Sisson et al., 2006)
Road type	A data set on the classification of all road segments.	Prevalence of certain road types has negative effect.	(1) (Asadi-Shekari et al., 2015; Hardinghaus et al., 2021; Ito & Biljecki, 2021; Kamel et al., 2020; Krenn et al., 2015; Langerød Rugtvedt, 2019; Munira et al., 2021; Wout, 2022) (2) (Aranda-Balboa et al., 2020; Broberg & Sarjala, 2015; De Meester et al., 2014; Rahman et al., 2020; Shaaban & Abdur-Rouf, 2020; Sisson et al., 2006)
Collisions	A spatial dataset on the occurrence of collisions that involved a bicyclist.	Negative.	(1) (Codina et al., 2022; Kamel et al., 2020; Lin & Wei, 2018; Motta, 2017) (2) (Bao et al., 2023; Scheiner et al., 2019) (3) (Lee et al., 2020)
School site entrance location and school zones signage	Data set on the presence of school zones and position of school entrance.	Positive.	(2) (Rothman et al., 2022; Shaaban & Abdur-Rouf, 2020)
Criminality	A dataset on the rate of criminal offences occurring in the area, or a subjective data rating the perception of crime-safety in the area.	Negative.	(1) (Arellana et al., 2020) (2) (Aranda-Balboa et al., 2020; Wangzom et al., 2023)
Pedestrian traffic flow	A data on pedestrian traffic volumes in each area.	Positive.	(2) (Aranda-Balboa et al., 2020; Wangzom et al., 2023)

Table 6. School bikeability index, indicators related to surrounding environment.

Indicator	Necessary data	Impact	Reference ¹
Slope	Elevation data. Ideally, elevation data of the road network would be also available.	Negative.	(1) (Arellana et al., 2020; Asadi-Shekari et al., 2015; Hardinghaus et al., 2021; Hartanto, 2017; Ito & Biljecki, 2021; Karolemeas et al., 2022; Krenn et al., 2015; Lin & Wei, 2018; Porter et al., 2020; Wout, 2022) (2) (Bao et al., 2023; Ghekiere et al., 2014; Goodman et al., 2019; Sisson et al., 2006)
Aesthetic and attractiveness	Design characteristics of the built environment. Ideally, a subjective judgement of area aesthetics and attractiveness to be cycled.	Positive.	(1) (Arellana et al., 2020; Hartanto, 2017; Ito & Biljecki, 2021; Karolemeas et al., 2022; Lin & Wei, 2018) (2) (Rahman et al., 2020) (3) (Lee et al., 2020)
Air quality	Air pollution data with detailed resolution.	Poor air quality has negative influence.	(1) (Ito & Biljecki, 2021; Lin & Wei, 2018; Porter et al., 2020; Ros-McDonnell et al., 2020; Wout, 2022)
Natural elements	A dataset on the presence (and extension) of natural elements, such as parks and forests.	Positive.	(1) (Arellana et al., 2020; Hardinghaus et al., 2021; Hartanto, 2017; Ito & Biljecki, 2021; Karolemeas et al., 2022; Krenn et al., 2015; Lin & Wei, 2018; Porter et al., 2020; Wout, 2022) (2) (Aranda-Balboa et al., 2020; De Vries et al., 2010; Ghekiere et al., 2014; Van Kann et al., 2015)

These areas can be delineated using existing data on school attendance or estimated based on a specified distance from the school. A reasonable distance for cycling to school is approximately 2 km (Lee et al., 2020). The buffer area around a school should be defined using the road network rather than a Euclidean distance, as the latter may not accurately reflect the actual travel distance (Liu et al., 2020).

The final index can be constructed by mathematically combining empirical values from various indicators. These indicator values can be categorised, with each category assigned a different score, and higher scores are given to values that most strongly support bikeability (Winters et al., 2013), or they can be normalised relative to minimum or maximum values (Ito & Biljecki, 2021). Certain indicators, such as bike parking availability, can be operationalised as binary values, receiving a normalised score of either 0 or 1, or other minimum and maximum scores.

The common practice is to assign weights to the indicators based on their importance, which can be determined using several methods, including survey-based and literature review-based approaches, expert surveys, the analytic hierarchy process, and a weighted linear combination model (Ahmed et al., 2024). Given the significant role parents play in deciding their children's mode of travel, constructing the final index should take into account the parents' perspective on the importance of the different indicators. Thus, weights derived from a survey targeting parents of school children is a suitable approach.

As highlighted throughout the text, certain indicators may have ambiguous or two-sided effects. For example, a higher number of intersections can be associated with active children's travel in a positive sense, reflecting good street connectivity, and a negative sense, due to the increased perception of safety risks (Scheiner et al., 2019). Similarly, the presence of natural elements can be positive if they are well-maintained, but negative

otherwise. Population density might also have a positive impact within certain middle-range values but could be problematic at low and very high levels. In such cases, it is important to examine the local context to understand the exact effect of these indicators, and, if possible, to account for their interaction with other variables or support their use with some subjective data. These possibilities should be explored for the area in question, the data availability, and the policy context.

5. Discussion and conclusion

Given the limited success in promoting cycling as a mode of transport, the constrained funds allocated to cycling investments, and the declining trend of cycling to and from school, there is a pressing need for synthesized knowledge that can be readily applied.

While the concept of bikeability has gained attention in recent years, existing literature does not usually distinguish between different groups of cyclists, such as children cycling to school, and neglects to address their specific needs. This paper argues for the development of a distinct measurement method for assessing bikeability to school that accounts for children's unique requirements, distinct from those of adults. Importantly, since caretakers are the primary decision-makers regarding their children's mode of transport, their perspective on cycling infrastructure and the school environment must be considered. This paper contributes such insights in the form of a set of indicators for evaluating school bikeability in a given area. In other words, it aims to illuminate the extent to which cycling to school is feasible for a child in a specific area and context, and thereby facilitate targeted strategies to enhance school bikeability conditions.

It addresses this need and proposes an outline for a school bikeability index, consisting of 4 domains and 24 indicators. It builds upon existing general bikeability measures and specifies additional indicators that affect children's bikeability to school, namely, bicycle parking at school, speed limits on roads near schools, the presence of speed-limiting measures, and the location of school entrances.

The presented list of indicators for school bikeability would provide important insights, for instance, to identify weak points around each school. Such insights could help city transport planners and school officials decide where to direct investments and funding to create safe and secure cycling routes to and from school. Additionally, it could be used to test different scenarios to understand how varying investments might affect the school area's bikeability.

The current study also revealed several streams for future research. Researchers could build upon this set of indicators, aiming to construct and apply the index to specific locations, while validating the importance of the indicators. It would be especially interesting to explore how these indicators interact in the decision-making process of caretakers when making decisions about allowing their children to cycle to school. This validation is important because various factors might have different impacts depending on the specific location. Although the study aims to create a geographically independent set of bikeability indicators, cycling as a mode of transport and a topic in transport research has historically been more prominent in Western countries. The determinants of cycling to school have often been studied in car-based societies such as the USA,

Canada, and Australia, whereas safety in cycling, especially regarding children, has been studied more extensively in Western and Northern Europe. Consequently, some of the findings here may not be universally representative.

Additionally, the outline of indicators could benefit from a broader perspective, spanning beyond physical environment determinants, which play a major role in existing bikeability indices. While it is essential to consider the increased computational burden, the list of indicators could be enriched by subjective measures such as attitudes, perceptions of traffic safety and crime, stranger danger, perceived long distance, lack of social support, and social norms. These indicators were intentionally omitted here, but their importance is acknowledged. A review that distinguishes between objective and subjective indicators (Castañón & Ribeiro, 2021) and reviews focusing on parental barriers to active travel to school (Aranda-Balboa et al., 2020; Wangzom et al., 2023) could serve as a starting point. The importance of including the perceived safety threats is also understood by the “safety paradox” noted by Thomsen (2005) which states that parents’ perception of safety threats may increase even though the actual traffic threats have decreased.

Perceptions and attitudes may play different roles depending on a geographical location and culture. For instance, in Denmark, Finland, the UK, and Portugal, parental perceptions of traffic safety and stranger danger have been cited as reasons for driving children to school by car, while, in other locations, traffic safety concerns and distance to school were identified as the primary factors (Huertas-Delgado et al., 2017; Wangzom et al., 2023). Although inconclusive, there seems to be an evidence that in environments where cycling is less common, the distance to school and parental perceptions of safety and security when travelling actively to school are the main barriers to allowing children to cycle to school. In countries where cycling is more common, these factors seem to be less prominent and are combined with factors such as stranger danger, social support, and the convenience of driving. Distance, traffic safety, and security appear to be the baseline indicators for a higher share of active travel modes on the way to school. These findings demonstrate the imperfect transferability of findings from studies focusing on school active travel. Thus, validating the index in different geographical areas, characterised by different mode share of cycling, levels of safety, and overall perceptions towards cycling to school would be a valuable next step.

Moreover, while the indicators are specific to school bikeability, there is no distinction between the exact types of schools and the relevant age ranges of children. It has been documented earlier that caretakers’ decisions regarding allowing their children to bike to school may be influenced by the children’s age, suggesting that the determinants and their importance could vary depending on the age group. This variation in determinants based on children’s age is illustrated by different studies conducted in Sweden that found different reasons for driving children to school – whether it is the wish to accompany the child and the convenience of car use for older children or the practicality of driving and the dangerous school route for children including younger age groups (Anund et al., 2013; Westman et al., 2017). Future research could, therefore, focus on understanding the differences in the school bikeability index, depending on the type of school or children’s age.

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